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Annotation

The article describes the concepts of family and marriage and talks about the role and formation of the family in society. It is possible to learn feedback on the misunderstandings that arise in today's family relationships and ways to solve them. In addition, information is provided about the purpose of the marriage structure and the consequences of the marriage structure for the cause.

Keywords: family, marriage, society, treatment, matrilocal family, nuclear family, group, kinship, social attitudes, economic attitudes, ideological attitudes.

Introduction In the sacred religion of Islam, family building is considered the most important and extremely responsible task in a person's life. Because the period of a person's life after marriage will be beautiful, good, or vice versa will largely depend on this responsible event. Also, the importance of the family is very important for society. Because the family is an integral part of the main branch of society. The healthier the family, the healthier the community. The unity, harmony of the family is the unity, harmony of society. A person grows up in a family, matures, receives elementary upbringing in the family. Qualities such as Knowledge, a culture of mutual treatment, rational attitude to the environment, hard work, self-esteem are formed first of all in the family environment.

Main part. A family is a social group made up of people connected by blood-kinship, kinship (through marriage), or co-settlement. In many societies, the family serves as the main institution for the socialization of children. Anthropologists classify families into matrilocal (mother and her children), married (when they have children, they are called nuclear family), and blood-related (nuclear family and mother-in-law coexist) types.

A family is a small group based on marriage or childbirth. Its members are intertwined with the unity, mutual assistance and spiritual responsibility of the monk. The most important social tasks of the family are to continue the human race, raise children, effectively organize the living conditions and free time of family members. Although family relations are considered a relatively independent phenomenon, they are determined by the existing social, economic, ideological relations in society and change under their influence. Accordingly, each society establishes a suitable family type, family relations, changing.

The family has not existed in the history of society for a long time. In the first stage of the primitive communal system, when individuals were living in swarms, the relationship between the sexes did not have a specific order, and all men and women in the swarm were considered common spouses to each other. In the process of historical progress, sexual relations began to be slowly regulated. At first, sexual relations between parents and children, and then between brothers and sisters were prohibited, and a group Family appeared, but in these families, as yet, the couple's marriage did not have a stable separate form. During this period, the natural factor completed its task, that is, blood-relatives were excluded from the circle of sexual relations, sexual relations became only a male and a female relationship.

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Marriage is an alliance concluded on the basis of mutual consent of representatives of both sexes. Since marriage is a sudden basis in the formation of a family, it is regulated not only by the norms of morality, but by special legislation.

Results and discussion

The birth of a new family is not a continuation of the old (parent)! This is a new system and it is more priority (important) than the parent. However, putting the child in the first place in your life, the husband in the second place, and yourself in the third place is also incredibly destructive for the family and the child. Your dedication will sooner or later become the fault of the child for the fact that he lives at all. Take care of yourself first, then create a successful relationship with your spouse, then your relationship with your child will improve on its own. If you have a closer relationship with your child than with your husband, then the husband gradually loses his reputation for you and is pushed to the edge of the family, and the child can play the role of a psychological substitute for you. spoils the child's life. If the girl played the role of a psychological wife for her father (a very close relationship) or was rejected by him, she consciously does not look for a father in men - and men do not like this role. And reverse. No matter how the relationship between your child and your spouse develops, try not to interfere with them.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that before starting a family, future young family members should well understand what marriage and family are, what are its functions and the purpose of starting a family. Preparing young people for family, preparing for the choice of a spouse, the formation of communication skills are important tasks. The increase in the number of deductions is also a sign that the above tasks are not performed on time or at all.

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